

CONDENSATIONS OF ARYL DIAZONIUM SALTS WITH REACTIVE UNSATURATED COMPOUNDS. PART IV. ACTION OF ARYL DIAZONIUM CHLORIDES WITH α -METHYLACRYLIC ACID

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With α -methylacrylic acid ($R=Me$), $CH_2=C(R)COOH$ (I), the diazo reactions go to yield α -methylcinnamic acids, showing β -arylation. This clarification was needed in connection with a study of itaconic acid (I, $R=CH_2COOH$), also carrying an α -substituent.

Rai and Mathur (this *Journal*, 1947, 10, 413) reacted various aryl diazonium chlorides, carrying a negative substituent, with acrylic acid in the presence of sodium acetate and copper chloride and found that the reaction afforded workable yields of cinnamic acids:

The traces of the α -chlorinated hydrocinnamic acids which might have also formed in the reaction seemed to have reverted to the unsaturated acids readily. The use of acetone advanced by Meerwein and co-workers (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, ii, 152, 237) for such reactions was found to be unnecessary with acrylic acid. Also, in the formation of cinnamic acids by this procedure, the aryl group had linked itself in a way conforming to Koelsch's β -arylation rule (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 413).

The occurrence of β -arylation (Koelsch, *loc. cit.*) in the case of certain $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated carbonyl compounds

has so far been observed with those compounds only which do not carry any substituent in the α -position. However, in connection with the study of a reaction of *p*-chlorobenzene diazonium chloride with itaconic acid

it became imperative to know definitely if in an acrylic acid having a substituent α to the carboxylic group, the reactivity of the double bond and the orientation of the aryl group were in any way different from those found in the parent acid. To decide these points, *p*-chlorobenzene diazonium chloride and certain other aryl diazonium chlorides have been condensed with α -methylacrylic acid and the results are recorded in the present communication.

When *p*-chlorobenzene diazonium chloride is reacted with α -methylacrylic acid in the presence of copper chloride and sodium acetate, the solid reaction product upon

extraction with aqueous sodium bicarbonate gives an unsaturated monobasic acid (m. p. 119). That this acid is *p*-chloro- α -methylcinnamic acid is shown by its identity with the acidic product obtained by reacting *p* chlorobenzene diazonium chloride with citraconic acid. The latter reaction, as is already known in other cases (cf. Dhingra and Mathur, this *Journal*, 1947, 25, 123), must have yielded the above named acid according to the equation formulated below.

Results similar to that of the *p*-chlorobenzene diazonium chloride are obtained by working with *p*-nitro- and *m*-nitrobenzene diazonium chlorides and β -naphthalene diazonium chloride, the products being α -methyl- β -arylacrylic acids. Their identity has been established with the corresponding acids which can be obtained by reacting the above diazonium halides with citraconic acid (vide Dhingra and Mathur, *loc. cit.*) Opportunity has thus been taken to do the latter reactions all over again, but using no acetone whereby the cinnamic acids have been obtained in improved yields.

In the reactions with *p*-chlorobenzene diazonium chloride, no intermediate halogen adduct e. g.,

has been isolated. Neither is there any indication of the formation of an unsaturated hydrocarbon e. g., *p*-chloroisopropenylbenzene $\text{CH}_2 = \text{C}(\text{CH}_3) - \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$, which would have been present in the reaction mixture if coupling were α to the COOH group.

The results substantiate the fact that the aryl group would be oriented to the β -position, even when there is an alkyl group present α to the COOH group in acrylic acid thus :

However, if the yields of the acids from the methyl compound are compared with those from acrylic acid, they are found to be lower.

TABLE I

Amine diazotised. (M/40)	Yield with (M/40)	
	α -Methylacrylic acid.	Acrylic acid.
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	13.02%	27.8%
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	20.26	60.1
<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	11.8	28.3
β -Naphthylamine	8.6	10.05

An alkyl substituent in the position α to the COOH group thus appears to weaken the response for radical attacked in an acrylic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

The citraconic anhydride needed for the preparation of α -methylacrylic acid and citraconic acid needed for some experiments were prepared by the method of Shriner, Ford and Rolls ("Org. Syn", Coll. Vol. II, 1943, p. 140).

For the preparation of an aqueous solution of α -methylacrylic acid, the following procedure was adopted. Citraconic anhydride (40 g.) was saturated with hydrogen chloride gas at ordinary temperature (vide Fittig and Landolt, *Annalen*, 1877, 189, 83). After keeping in the refrigerator for 2 nights α -chloro- α -methylsuccinic acid separated (m.p. 129°.) The latter was first neutralised with alkali and then made fairly alkaline and boiled under reflux (cf. Fittig and Prehn, *ibid.*, pp. 41, 51) for 3 or 4 hours. It was then treated with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (2*N*) and steam distilled till about 600 c.c. of the distillate were obtained. The latter reacted strongly acidic and showed unsaturation. The sodium salt (2.05 g.), prepared out of a little portion of the distillate, gave on ignition with sulphuric acid 1.33 g. Na₂SO₄. (Found: Na, 21.01. C₄H₅O₂Na requires Na, 21.3 per cent). The amount of α -methylacrylic acid in the solution was determined alkalimetrically. According to analysis, 100 c.c. of the aqueous solution were to be used for reacting an *M*/₄₀ acid.

Condensations of p-Chlorobenzene diazonium Chloride with α -Methylacrylic Acid.—*p*-Chloroaniline (3.2 g., *M*/₄₀) in 2.5 times the molecular proportions of hydrochloric acid was diazotised in the usual manner (total volume ca. 35 c.c.). The filtered diazotised base was added to the aqueous solution containing α -methylacrylic acid (*M*/₄₀, 100 c. c. soln.) and copper chloride (1 g.) and sodium acetate (5.75 g.) in water (20 c.c.) The reaction mixture was stirred throughout and the temperature maintained at about 30°-35°. There was a brisk effervescence for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and it went on slowly for further 3 to 4 hours. The reaction mixture was filtered; the black solid residue was washed with a little water and finally extracted with cold 10% sodium bicarbonate solution. The extract was acidified with hydrochloric acid, when an acid separated, yield 0.6 g. It did not contain any halogen removable by strong aqueous caustic soda. The acid was recrystallised from water as needles, m. p. 119°. It decolorised 1% potassium permanganate and bromine water. (Found: Equiv., 193.5; Cl, 17.82. C₈H₆O₂Cl requires equiv., 196.5; Cl, 18.05 per cent).

The sodium bicarbonate-insoluble matter was extracted with ether, the ether layer washed with aqueous alkali and then with water and the ether removed. A very small amount of an oily matter remained, which did not decolorise 1% permanganate.

Condensations of p-Chlorobenzene diazonium Chloride with Citraconic Acid in the presence of Sodium Acetate and Copper Chloride, but without Acetone.—The diazotised amine (*M*/₄₀) was condensed with citraconic acid (3.25 g., *M*/₄₀) in the presence of cupric chloride (1 g.) and sodium acetate (5.75 g.), the total bulk of the reaction mixture being about 50 c. c. The solid separating was extracted with aqueous sodium bicarbonate as before, and the extracted acid liberated with hydrochloric acid, yield 1.7 g.

(34%). It was recrystallised from hot water in needles, m.p. 120°. (Found: Equiv., 195; Cl, 17.8. $C_8H_6O_2Cl$ requires equiv., 196.5; Cl, 18.05 per cent). Mixed m. p. with the *p*-chloro acid obtained from α -methylacrylic acid, 119°.

Condensations of p-Nitro-, m-Nitrobenzene diazonium Chlorides and β -Naphthalene diazonium Chloride with α -Methylacrylic Acid.—The respective diazotised bases (*M/40*) were condensed with α -methylacrylic acid (*M/10*, 100 c. c. soln.), the experiments having been conducted in the manner similar to that of the *p*-chloro analogue. The resulting unsaturated acids were isolated after keeping the reaction mixture overnight, but the yields varied on longer standing. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Amine diazotised (<i>M/40</i>).	Unsaturated monobasic acids.			α -Methyl- β -arylacrylic acids		
	A (From α -methylacrylic acid)			(From citraconic acid)		
	Yield	M.p	Equiv. weight Found. Calc.	M.p & mixed m p. with (A)		
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	1.0 g. 20.26%	207°	202 207	207°		
<i>m</i> -Nitroaniline	0.62 11.8	195	203.4 207	196		
β -Naphthylamine	0.46 8.6	117-22°	206 212	117-22°		

The nature of the acids was decided by running parallel experiments with citraconic acid; these were done previously in the presence of acetone (vide Dhingra and Mathur, *loc. cit.*) but in the present investigation its use was omitted. By this omission the yields of the cinnamic acids could be improved by about 20 to 50%.

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